

POTENTIAL IMPACT OF CHANGING INTERNATIONAL SITUATION

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ABSTRACT

A number of recent international developments have the potential of affecting export of U.S. products to foreign markets. It has been suggested that the Federal Communications Commission should participate with other U.S. Government agencies in the process of developing, among other things, a Mutual Recognition Agreement for conformity assessment. While the FCC's primary mission is the promotion and protection of radio communications in this country, we are also interested in ensuring that our programs for controlling electromagnetic interference (EMI) promote international trade. The purpose of this paper is to provide a brief overview of some of these recent international developments and present some of the issues facing industry and the agency.

CHANGING WORLD SITUATION

The following provides a partial list of recent international developments that have the potential of affecting trade. Please note that this paper is not intended to provide an in-depth discussion of any of these topics.

- The General Agreement on Tariff and Trade (GATT) has specific provisions for standards-related measures to preclude technical barriers to trade. Specifically, it contains rights and obligations of trading partners to ensure that standards do not impede trade. Efforts by most countries of the world to update and extend the rules and commitments governing international trade have been under way for over seven years in what is known as the Uruguay Round of Multilateral Trade Negotiations (MTN) of GATT. Included in these talks is a proposal relating to certification systems. The proposal seeks improved rules on the operation, transparency and mutual recognition of certification systems under the agreement.
The North American Free Trade Agreement (NAFTA) affirms for the three trading partners (Canada, Mexico and U.S.A.) the rights and obligations relating to standards-related measures under the GATT Agreement on Technical Barriers to Trade. In addition, it encourages the use of international standards to the extent practical. It also paves the way for the three parties to accept, approve, license or otherwise recognize conformity assessment bodies in the territory of another party on terms no less favorable than those accorded to such bodies in its territory.
The Commission of European Communities (EC) is in the process of promoting the single market concept to promote unobstructive exchange of products among its member states. While many aspects of the process remain unclear, at best, it is clear that the way of doing business with EC member states is changing. A product manufactured in one EC member state will have unrestricted market access to any other member state, provided it complies with all EC Directives and carries the "CE" mark attesting to its compliance. A number of EC Directives have been adopted, which

establish broad requirements in a particular area of concern, e.g., the Electromagnetic Compatibility (EMC) and Telephone Terminal Equipment (TTE) Directives. Also, a product may be subject to more than one directive. A partial listing of EC Directives is provided in Figure 1.

FIGURE 1 -- PARTIAL LIST OF EC DIRECTIVES

Table with 3 columns: Directive, Title, Applicability. Rows include: 88/378 Toy Safety, 87/404 Pressure Vessels, 89/336 EMC, 89/392 Machinery, 89/686 Protective Equipment, 90/384 Weighing Instrument, 90/385 Medical Devices, 73/23 Low Voltage, 90/396 Gas Appliances, 91/263 TTE, Medical Devices, Constr. Products.

Conformity assessment schemes have been developed to ensure compliance with applicable technical standards. Depending on the product and applicable EC directive, a manufacturer may test and self-

approve his product. For most products, the manufacturer must have the product tested and approved by a Competent Body or a Notified Body. The EMC Directive ostensibly allows the manufacturer to self-approve his product, provided the applicable standards have been adopted. To date all the standards needed to show compliance with the EMC Directive have not been adopted. In this instance, compliance may be determined by using a procedure called the Technical Construction File route, which must be accomplished by a Competent Body. Both Notified and Competent Bodies must be physically located in the EC, unless a third party agreement (MRA) has been established.

- Mutual Recognition Agreement (MRA) is the term the EC is using to indicate that an agreement has been negotiated with a non-EC member on conformity assessment. Briefly, it establishes guidelines for access to the EC market for a non-EC member based on conformity assessment of the product to meet EC Directives. The EC Commission has indicated a willingness to negotiate an MRA with the U.S., as well as other countries. In response to requests from U.S. trade associations, the Department of Commerce has started the process of discussing MRA's with the EC. An initial exploratory meeting was held in Brussels in October 1992. A second exploratory meeting is scheduled for May 1993 in Washington.
- Other administrations have indicated that they also wish to establish reciprocity agreements (MRA) for conformity assessment with the U.S.A. Specifically, Singapore and the Republic of Korea have indicated that they want to initiate talks on acceptance of each other's test data and approvals.
- The International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC) is an international voluntary standards making organization. The International Special Committee on Radio Interference (CISPR) is a special committee of the IEC. It is responsible for developing recommendations for controlling harmful interference from unintentional radiators. To date, it has developed worldwide consensus Electromagnetic Compatibility (EMC) standards for home appliances, information technology equipment, receivers and others. The Commission of European Communities (EC) has agreed in principal to use IEC standards for assuring compliance with EC Directives. Moreover, the IEC has established a parallel procedure of voting to expedite the adoption of standards to meet the needs of the EC. As a result, there is more emphasis on the use of international standards instead of regional or national standards.

FCC REQUIREMENTS

At this point, it might be useful to briefly describe FCC technical standards and compliance requirements which, as you might expect, were developed to meet the developing needs of radio communications in the U.S.A. Over the years, the FCC adopted a number of technical standards for transmitters and other equipment to increase frequency sharing and to protect radio communications. For the most part, we adhere to ITU Radio Regulations and international standards developed by CCIR and CCITT for radio transmission equipment.

In addition, there are a number of region specific requirements for equipment operated in the U.S.A. Technical requirements for licensed transmitters are codified throughout the FCC Rules, which are divided into rule parts, each relating to a particular radio service, e.g., Part 73 contains technical standards for

the broadcast transmitters, as well as other operational requirements. Standards for non-licensed equipment, such as computers and ISM equipment, are codified in Parts 15 and 18 of the FCC Rules, respectively. The purpose of the latter standards is to ensure that unintentional radio frequency (RF) emissions from these devices do not cause harmful electromagnetic interference (EMI) to radio communications. It is important to note that in some instances the FCC is beginning to use industry standards in lieu of adopting mandatory standards. A synopsis of the FCC requirements for unintentional radiators subject to Part 15 of the FCC Rules is contained in Figure 2.

FIGURE 2 - FCC REQUIREMENTS FOR UNINTENTIONAL RADIATORS

DEVICES COVERED: Digital Devices (Class A -- commercial & Class B -- residential), Radio Receivers (30-960 MHz) and CB Receivers, TV Interface Devices (VCRs, camcorders, etc.), Cable System Terminal Devices

EXEMPTIONS: Home appliances, Medical devices, Test equipment, Industrial and public utility plant equipment, Electronics in vehicles, Electronics with clocks < 1.705 MHz, Devices with power consumption ≤ 6 nW

RADIATED LIMIT: (using C63.4-1991)

<u>Frequency</u>	<u>Class A</u>	<u>Class B</u>
30 - 88 MHz	90 (µV/m at 10 m)	100 (µV/m at 3 m)
88 - 216 MHz	150 (µV/m at 10 m)	150 (µV/m at 3 m)
216 - 960 MHz	210 (µV/m at 10 m)	200 (µV/m at 3 m)
> 960 MHz	300 (µV/m at 10 m)	500 (µV/m at 3 m)

CONDUCTED LIMIT: (using C63.4-1991)

<u>Frequency</u>	<u>Class A</u>	<u>Class B</u>
0.45 - 1.705 MHz	1000 (µV)	250 (µV)
1.705 - 30 MHz	3000 (µV)	250 (µV)

ADMINISTRATIVE REQUIREMENTS:

1. Labels and user information required
2. Equipment Authorization Required

Certification - TV interface devices
P.C. & peripherals
CB & scanning receivers
Superregenerative receivers

Notification - Other receivers
Cable term. device

Verification - TV/FM receivers
Cable switch
Class A device
Class B device
External supplies
Other devices

To ensure compliance with its technical standards, an equipment authorization program was developed. A brief explanation of the various programs and applicability is provided in Figure 3. The specific equipment authorization is specified in the rule part for each type of equipment. In each case the equipment must be tested for compliance and either a grant of equipment authorization is issued by the FCC or a label placed on the equipment. For certain types of tests, e.g., personal computers, a description of the measurement facility must be on file with the FCC. Compliance with the technical standards and administrative requirements is a prerequisite for legal importation and marketing of the equipment in the U.S.A.

FIGURE 3 -- EQUIPMENT AUTHORIZATION PROGRAM

TYPE	SUBMISSION REQUIRED	EXAMPLES
VERIFICATION ³	NO	FM AND TV RECEIVERS CLASS A DIGITAL DEVICES
NOTIFICATION ³	YES ¹	NON-BROADCAST RECEIVERS
CERTIFICATION ³	YES ¹	INTENTIONAL RADIATORS, PERSONAL COMPUTERS AND ASSOCIATED PERIPHERALS, CORDLESS TELEPHONES
TYPE ACCEPTANCE ³	YES ¹	LICENSED TRANSMITTERS
TELEPHONE	YES ²	TELEPHONE TERMINAL EQUIPMENT

Note 1: FCC Form 731, technical description, photographs, test data, fees, user's manual. For notification, only fees and Form 731 plus a statement of compliance are required.

Note 2: Equipment attached to the telephone network must comply with the requirements of Part 68 to ensure protection of the telephone network. Submission includes: FCC Form 730, technical description, and report of measurements and fees.

Note 3: Compliance with the technical and administrative requirements are a prerequisite for the legal importation and marketing of such equipment.

Telephone standards and a telephone registration program were also established under Part 68 of the FCC Rules to protect the telephone network. Terminal equipment attached to the telephone network must be tested and registered with the FCC to ensure that it does not load or otherwise harm the network. This program is administered by the Common Carrier Bureau of the FCC.

POTENTIAL IMPACT AND CONCERNS

As mentioned above, the FCC's primary responsibility is the promotion and protection of radio communications in the U.S.A. Other agencies, such as the Department of Commerce and Department of State, have the primary responsibility for promoting trade. Nevertheless, the FCC is certainly interested in assisting U.S. manufacturers, and in ensuring that our programs promote trade. To this extent, here are a few examples of our efforts to help U.S. manufacturers.

As evidence of FCC support of U.S. industry, we have extensively participated for a number of years in the development of CISPR Publication 22, which is an international standard for controlling RF emissions from ITE. (This is one of the standards the EC Commission has adopted for demonstrating compliance with the EMC Directive.) In addition, we recently proposed in a rule making proceeding, designated FCC Docket 92-152, to allow manufacturers the option of complying with either CISPR-22 or Part 15 to show compliance with Part 15-B. The comments received in response to this proposal were overwhelmingly in favor of the choice. This new ruling, which is expected to be adopted later this year, will greatly assist manufacturers by reducing the number of standards and tests for products marketed worldwide.

Additional evidence of our support to industry is the adoption in the proceeding in FCC Docket No. 89-44 of

the industry standard C63.4-1991 as the procedure the FCC will use in evaluating the compliance of digital devices. This procedure was adopted after extensive meetings of C63, in which industry representatives and FCC staff hammered out the details of a consensus test procedure. It should also be noted that many aspects of C63.4-1991 have been incorporated into CISPR-22, which again will make it easier on manufacturers by simplifying the tests for worldwide products.

During the last two years, there has been considerable discussion about the Common Market and the issue of harmonization of standards and conformity assessment in the EC. U.S. manufacturers are quite correctly concerned about the changing market access requirements to EC member states. Considerable effort has been extended by U.S. industry through trade associations, such as American National Standards Institute (ANSI) and others, and the U.S. Government to understand the evolving market access requirements of the EC. In a few product areas, there now seems to be convergence of understanding of the situation.

For example, Information Technology Equipment (ITE) has been identified as a high priority export item for U.S. suppliers accounting for over \$13 billion in exports to Europe. For this reason, the Computer and Business Manufacturers Association (CBEMA), Telecommunications Industry Association (TIA), American Electronics Association (AEA), National Electrical Manufacturers Association (NEMA) and others have requested the Department of Commerce to proceed as quickly as possible to schedule MRA negotiations with the EC. CBEMA identified five EC Directives that the IT industry is concerned with: EMC, Low Voltage, TTE, Visual Display Terminals (VDT), and Weights and Measures.

The first meeting with EC representatives was held in Brussels in October 1992. The second meeting is scheduled to be held in Washington in May 1993. Both of these meetings were mainly exploratory in content to establish the framework of future negotiations. An important outcome of the first meeting was the draft model MRA on conformity offered for discussions by the EC representatives. Among other things, it proposes that both signatories of the agreement undertake to grant mutual acceptance of reports, certificates and marks of each party. In other words, a product tested and approved in the U.S. would be freely marketed in the EC. Conversely, EC member states would expect the same privilege for those products for which an MRA is accepted. This clause represents a substantial concern for the FCC. Does this mean that Competent Bodies should grant equipment authorizations the same as the FCC? There is some question whether this is permissible under the FCC operating authority, i.e., the Communication Act of 1934, as amended. Should the FCC change its equipment authorization programs and standards for compliance? If so, how should they be changed?

It should be emphasized that we are in the very early stages of understanding what is to be included in an MRA and how it will be implemented. The question should also be asked if it is desirable to negotiate such an agreement with the EC. What about similar agreements for other countries? Which countries and when? Where is this leading? Assuming for the moment that it is in our interest to have such agreements, a number of issues need to be decided, which may, among other things, include:

- Scope It seems that initial interest should be limited to particular product sectors where there is substantial international trade. What should this encompass? Which products, standards, tests, etc.?

Does this mean that each party must recognize each other's certificates? What if there are different standards?

- Laboratory Competency Other parts of the world are placing more emphasis on the competency of the laboratory performing the measurements. Some of these schemes are quite elaborate and costly to implement. The FCC on the other hand has adopted a scheme of relying on the test data submitted by the manufacturer, or if they are unable to perform the tests, an outside test laboratory. The data we require from the manufacturer and test firm is minimal, compared to the types and extent of data required to become a Competent Body. Instead we have been relying on a system of review (certification and type acceptance) for that equipment for which we have a high level of concern and auditing when necessary. This raises the question of whether the FCC should consider laboratory accreditation criteria similar to that being established by the EC. Should it be mandatory or voluntary? Should we use one of the existing or developing criteria for laboratories? What are the cost/benefits of such a program?
- Standards The EMI requirements in Parts 15 and 18 were promulgated as a result of actual cases of interference. They are considered minimal to control interference. Most of the equipment we regulate is subject to a self-approval procedure (verification) by the manufacturer. In the case of the ITE, only personal computers and associated peripherals are subject to approval (certification) by the FCC. It has been suggested that we should move this category of equipment into verification to satisfy the EC condition for mutual recognition of grants. Will this help the negotiations? Notwithstanding international developments, the FCC has historically reviewed the standards and authorization requirements for products and relaxed the rules where there is stability of compliance and relatively few risks of interference. FM and TV broadcast receivers are a good example where the equipment no longer was a prime source of interference and we reduced the equipment authorization requirement from certification to verification. While we continue to look at our programs, it is not clear that all those factors are present for personal computers. Moreover, it is not clear what benefit we will obtain by moving PCs into verification.

These are some of the fundamental questions that need to be answered before we can proceed. There are many more questions yet to be raised and answered. Nevertheless, we will continue to monitor the situation and take whatever steps are necessary to assist U.S. manufacturers. In summary, we are very much aware of the developing changes in the world and are contemplating what measures the FCC should take to promote access of U.S. products to foreign markets. We are also receptive to eliminating multiple test procedures and approvals.

One final comment: the views expressed in this paper are those of the author and do not necessarily reflect those of the Commission or its staff.